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Wild-type Abl1 kinase targeting in TNBC with nilotinib.

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We present here evidence for a general oncogene targeting approach using a small molecule inhibitor of Abl1 kinase in TNBC for oncogene addiction.

Results

- a. We evaluated transcriptomic parameters relating to candidate oncogene or oncogene-kinase targetability: here, in TNBC.
- b. We previously described abundant expression of diverse oncogenes in human TNBC in vivo.
 - i. Specifically, we considered whether wild-type Abl1 kinase was targetable in TNBC with an imatinib-class Abl1 kinase inhibitor.
 - ii. Nilotinib binds both the BCR-ABL fusion oncogene found in human CML that is Ph+
 - iii. Nilotinib also binds with affinity the wild-type Abl1 kinase in isolation.
- c. Cellular output resulting from Abl1 kinase inhibition through Nilotinib antagonism of wild-type Abl1 kinase was evaluated in Hs587T TNBC cells with RNA-sequencing following in vitro pharmacologic target inhibition.
 - i. GSE210987
 - ii. TNBC cells treated with nilotinib or the EGFR/HER2 inhibitor lapatinib
- d. We observed transcriptional responses consistent with exposure to a chemotherapeutic agent: suitability of indication for nilotinib Abl1 kinase inhibition for chemotherapeutic interventions in oncogene-expressing cancers in the absence of BCR fusion events
- e. A central and definitive response to nilotinib in human TNBC cells was silencing of the Casitas B-cell lymphoma oncogene, *CBLB*.
 - i. Nilotinib but not lapatinib conferred CBLB oncogene silencing in TNBC cells.
- f. PIK2 and Cemip relief by nilotinib in Hs indicated possibility of general anti-proliferative function for a wild-type Abl1 kinase inhibitor in a cancer type actively expressing a suite of diverse oncogenes
- g. Abl1 wild-type oncogenic kinase inhibition in TNBC cells was associated with a significant immunologic response
 - i. Ccl2 induction
 - ii. Nfkb program changes related to senescence
 - iii. Il27ra induction
 - iv. CXCL8 silencing
- h. Ccng2 repression was a feature of Abl1 kinase inhibitor in TNBC cells
 - i. Non-coding RNA control by nilotinib in TNBC cells
 - i. LASTR: lncRNA associated with SART3 regulation of splicing
 - ii. LINC01605
 - iii. CYTOR
 - iv. PABIR family ncRNAs
- j. Steroid hormone metabolism enzymes were generally more securely controlled with nilotinib than lapatinib in vitro
 - i. Cyp26b1
 - ii. Cyp1b1 was similarly repressed
- k. Membrane biochemical aspects of transformed cells
 - i. Scn3a

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- I. Ets factor control
 - i. Modest regulation of Elk1 and Elk4 by nilotinib
- m. AR, ESR and PGR control
- n. Oncogenic chromatin modifier regulation
- o. Superior control of oncogenic homeobox activation by nilotinib.
- p. Absence of CDKN family activation by nilotinib in this cellular model was notable.

Discussion

We presented here positive evidence for disruption of oncogene signaling in TNBC with nilotinib using an *in vitro* experimental model of signaling in human TNBC cells.

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Citations

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